

Supplement to

The Expanding and Overlapping Roles of Institutional and Generalist Repositories

Building an Interoperable Data Repository Ecosystem Together

This document contains the full survey results referenced in the Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative's (GREI) presentation on June 17th at Open Repositories 2025.

Presentation information from the Open Repositories schedule is available at https://www.conftool.net/or2025/index.php?page=browseSessions&form_session=460&presentations=show

Event Description: Institutional repositories and generalist repositories are evolving to meet new challenges in research data sharing. The NIH Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) brings together seven leading generalist repositories to determine common data repository standards and enhance interoperability. Building on GREI's presentation at Open Repositories 2024, this presentation will explore how institutions are leveraging generalist repository infrastructure to support their data sharing needs.

Through real-world examples, we will demonstrate how different institutions utilize generalist repository features and services to enhance their data sharing workflows. The presentation will highlight various implementation approaches, from hosted solutions to self-managed instances, and examine how these platforms accommodate different disciplinary requirements and administrative preferences. We will share user experiences with different deposit models, curation workflows, and strategies for ensuring FAIR data sharing while maintaining institutional identity.

This session will benefit repository managers, librarians, research administrators, and others involved in institutional data sharing. Attendees will gain practical insights into how generalist repository infrastructure can support institutional needs, enhance research data discovery, and contribute to an interoperable repository ecosystem.

Survey Response from Marcy Vana

Associate Director, Bernard Becker Medical Library at Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis | <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7648-7116>

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Mendeley Data (a.k.a. Digital Commons Data) - <https://digitalcommonsdata.wustl.edu>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

There were a lot of features that we were looking for in a data repository. We wanted a data repository that could accommodate all file types and large file sizes and provide visibility of all the files in each record, including file name, type/extension, and size. We also wanted users to be able to download all the files in a record at once or just download individual files of interest. In addition, we were looking for support for ORCID iDs, the DataCite metadata schema, DOIs, versioning, licenses, linkages to related research outputs, access to draft records for peer review and more. Lastly, we wanted a data repository that could accommodate restricted access, as we knew that would be a need of our researchers since we are at a medical school.

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

We were very influenced by the new NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy. We have a lot of NIH funding at our medical school, so as a result we wanted a data repository that would allow us to best support our researchers in their data management and sharing compliance efforts.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

No.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

No.

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

Our repository is focused on datasets, and our users include faculty, staff, students, and trainees.

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

Submission to our data repository is mediated, and our data management and sharing team does extensive curation of the datasets before they are published.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

Our data repository is branded with Washington University School of Medicine branding, we have custom metadata fields, and we are frequently suggesting platform enhancements.

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

The ability to restrict access to a dataset has been a regular need.

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

The Digital Commons Data team at Elsevier has been great to work with. The team has been very open to our feedback and requests, which we really appreciate.

Is there a repository feature or function that you find particularly useful, interesting, and/or enjoyable to use?

The restricted access feature is a big one for us, being at a medical school. We use it regularly, and our data management and sharing team has put in a lot of great work to develop a collaborative workflow with our colleagues in the Human Research Protection Office and our Joint Research Office for Contracts.

[Responses continue on next page]

Survey Response from Maria Guerreiro

Head of Partnership Development at Dryad | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0010-6895>

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Dryad - <https://datadryad.org/>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

Most of the institutions we talk to want to work with Dryad because it's a turnkey, affordable and not-for-profit solution for data management and long-term preservation of data, that offers direct support and guidance for researchers and provides data and metadata curation.

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

A lot of the institutions we talk to highlight the importance of funder and government mandates, and the desire to preserve and make visible – with highly described metadata – the research data that their researchers are generating.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

Plenty of the institutions we talk to are exploring options, and ultimately decide to work with Dryad because of Dryad's outstanding service to individual researchers, and the time, resource and cost savings (vis-a-vis building their own infrastructure), while being not-for-profit. They appreciate that building their own repository is a very costly and challenging commitment in the immediate and long term, and that Dryad's 18 years of experience and leadership in this field is a much simpler, safer and better solution.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

This is the case with some of the institutions we talk to, and in often cases it may be due to the lack of internal resources to continue upholding to best practices for data management (e.g. ensuring there's in-house curation).

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

On Dryad, they only publish research data and code.

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

Because Dryad offers end-to-end, direct support to researchers, institutions integrate to Dryad, and provide, with Dryad's support, an overview of the scope and services, but there's minimal mediation, as researchers use Dryad directly and have direct support from our team of human curators throughout the submission, curation and publication processes.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

Dryad offers branding sign in pages, an admin dashboard for institutional managers, and technical integrations with existing systems (e.g. through single sign-on).

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

This is hugely variable across our institutional partners but usage is often strongly connected with disciplines where data deposit and sharing is an established or emerging practice.

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

Our institutional partners consistently highlight the quality of the service, specifically in the benefit of having Dryad providing direct one-to-one support to their researchers. This results in time and resource savings overall, and, given Dryad's robust curation and publication standards, the huge benefit of being able to guarantee compliance with the highest standards for data curation and data management practices.

Is there a repository feature or function that you find particularly useful, interesting, and/or enjoyable to use?

Our institutional partners value having their own admin dashboard for monitoring purposes, where they can track usage, impact and linkage to other research objects and funding, and Dryad's support for training and outreach to their researchers.

[Responses continue on next page]

Survey Response from Matt Carson

Head, Data Management & Technology at Northwestern University |
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4105-9220>

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Zenodo (a.k.a. InvenioRDM) - <https://prism.northwestern.edu/>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

Our IR supports faculty, staff, and students of the Feinberg School of Medicine. We wanted a repository that:

- Could be tailored to support the needs of our medical library and our university's CTSA.
- Could accommodate a wide range of research products to meet funders and publisher's open access requirements
- Promotes nontraditional research outputs (posters, protocols, lectures, etc.) as well as data

InvenioRDM is built on a modular framework that makes it customizable and extensible.

We also wanted to use a repository that had a robust community around it. InvenioRDM is used by CERN and many other institutions (<https://kt.cern/technologies/invenio>, <https://invenio-software.org/showcase/>). It has an active open source development community and the underlying technology (Python, Flask) is widely supported.

We liked the look, feel, and functionality of Zenodo and knew that it would soon be running on InvenioRDM. This gave us confidence that the platform would continue to be actively supported.

Some specific features we were looking for in a new repository were:

- Support FAIR standards
- integration of ORCID data
- Support for metadata-only records
- More robust support for datasets
- More advanced metrics on views and downloads for deposited records and collections to support reports on academic impact.
- Updated metadata model, more robust user profiles
- Support for acknowledgement of contributions of various stakeholders in clinical studies through a contributor role controlled vocabulary
- Support for community building among researchers

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

The CERN/InvenioRDM team has been very open and willing to work with us to develop modules that meet the data sharing, discovery, and interoperability goals for our institutional repository. Its modular framework also allows us to extend InvenioRDMs functionality to address COAR's next-generation repository guidelines.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

CERN and Northwestern were the two core partners in the effort to build InvenioRDM, along with about a dozen other national and international institutions. Since InvenioRDM is now the software underlying Zenodo and Zenodo is now part of GREI, we technically did both of these things.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

Yes, InvenioRDM replaced our existing institutional repository, which was established in 2015. The former IR stack was a combination of the back-end Fedora repository and Apache Solr (used for search indexing) and the web application framework Hydra (now called Samvera). Sufia was the front end and was an extension of Hydra, providing the user interface and associated features. We found ourselves needing functionality that wasn't provided by this implementation, and over the years the Galter team at the time made enhancements such as adding:

- The ability to mint DOIs and ARKs
- A IIIF image viewer (Mirador)
- Support for audio and video files

Even though the customizations added a lot of great functionality, we eventually painted ourselves into a corner with our current repository code, having customized it to a point that it would be very difficult to upgrade to what is now Samvera. Because of this, it made sense to explore new repository technology to see what our options were. During this time we received grant funding to support this transition and also began discussions with CERN about collaborating on development of a new repository (InvenioRDM).

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

Our IR supports faculty, staff, and students of the Feinberg School of Medicine at Northwestern.

We have a variety of research output types including data, code, and journal article collections as well as non-traditional research outputs such as posters, protocols, and lectures.

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

Our standard workflow requires IR users to self-deposit their records (we would like to use a mediated deposit model but do not have the capacity at this time). There are exceptions for complicated record creation or large data deposits. Our metadata librarians perform metadata checks and regular metadata audits to maintain quality.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

Software developers in our library customized our InvenioRDM instance. These modifications include:

- Customized front page, theming
- Some metadata additions (e.g., LoC Subject Headings, MeSH)
- Altmetric badges displayed on record pages
- Custom DOI widget
- Custom authentication module (using ForgeRock instead of the default KeyCloak as the identity provider)
- Customized admin panel to facilitate metadata curation and enhancement
- Truncated resource types (for improved UX)

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

Here are some simple stats on Prism:

- 93% of our records are open access
- Most of our content is articles (65%), followed by images (8%), text resources, learning objects, and study documentation.
- Most of the deposited files are PDFs (81%)
- Most of our record's subjects are identified using MeSH terms (75%). LCNAL and LCSH are also used.
- Our content skews towards the pediatric domain, specifically neurology, due to the inclusion of Pediatric Neurology Briefs (an open access journal).

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

InvenioRDM has many features that support FAIR standards, compliance, and impact tracking.

Is there a repository feature or function that you find particularly useful, interesting, and/or enjoyable to use?

We find the InvenioRDM/Zenodo community feature to be useful and particularly appealing to researchers. It allows users to create a shared meeting place for projects, subjects, institutions,

domains, or topics. Users can be invited to a community and soon will be able to request membership. Members can be assigned one of several roles in the community, and features for managing members, reviewing submissions, and curating content are provided.

When did the institution establish their relationship with your repository?

Northwestern established a connection with CERN in early 2019.

What support does the repository provider provide to the institution (e.g., implementation only, ongoing administration, data curation, etc.)?

CERN and the InvenioRDM/Zenodo teams provide the repository codebase, documentation, and user support via email and community chat free of charge. Installation, deployment, updates, and ongoing operational support is not provided.

[Responses continue on next page]

Survey Response from Clarke Iakovakis

Scholarly Services Librarian, Library at Oklahoma State University |

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9260-8456>

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Open Science Framework (OSF) - <https://osf.io/institutions/okstate>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

We prioritized features that support researchers throughout the full lifecycle of a project. Key requirements included the ability to add multiple collaborators, flexible privacy and sharing options, DOI minting for citation, support for all file types, affordability, use of open infrastructure, and a platform that requires minimal ongoing institutional support.

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

Although our institution does not currently have a formal open access or data sharing policy, it was important to select a repository that aligns with national and funder expectations. OSF meets the Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories as outlined by federal agencies, which strongly influenced our decision.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

While we maintain a DSpace institutional repository that supports limited data archiving, we lack the staffing and infrastructure to build and sustain a custom research data repository. We have been institutional supporters of OSF for a long time and it has built a lot of trust both within the library and in the institution in general.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

No. OSF complements our DSpace repository by offering features and workflows better suited for active research data management and collaboration.

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

Our primary users include library faculty and staff, who use the repository to archive presentation materials, research outputs, and workshop content. A number of faculty from across the university, including psychology, health sciences, sociology, agriculture, and

engineering, use the repository to share datasets, preprints, survey instruments, code, posters, and other project materials.

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

OSF operates primarily on a self-deposit model at OSU. The library does not currently provide extensive curation or quality control in OSF itself. However, our data services librarian works with faculty and students to promote good data management practices and offers guidance on repository use, especially during consultations and workshops. We are excited by the new Curator role OSF has launched, as that will give the data services librarian an avenue through which to work more directly with researchers using OSF for project management/organization and eventual data sharing.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

As an OSF member institution, our institutional OSF page is branded with our logo. We do not have any integrations particular to our institution, but it does integrate with our institutional OneDrive which is helpful because our institutional OneDrive by default does not support file sharing outside the institution.

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

Data files are mainly PPTX, CSVs, XLSX files, PDFs, DOCX and TXT files. The library is currently the most active user group, primarily for archiving presentation materials. Among academic departments, we see usage from psychology, sociology, agriculture, and engineering.

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

The main benefits include giving faculty an accessible, easy to use, low-barrier platform for sharing data and other research outputs. The fact that it works seamlessly across the research lifecycle and its flexible privacy controls are also appealing to different project types. Its mission-driven commitment to support open scholarship also aligns with our values. Integration with tools like OneDrive, GitHub, Dropbox, Zenodo etc. is also a major benefit as it allows researchers to connect their existing workflows. From an institutional perspective, OSF's open infrastructure and sustainability model allow us to support robust data sharing without the need for significant local technical or financial investment.

Is there a repository feature or function that you find particularly useful, interesting, and/or enjoyable to use?

My personal favorite use case is uploading my slide files, generating a short URL and adding that short URL to each slide to allow users to download my slides during my talks. Speaking with other faculty users, the most useful feature is, as I've mentioned, the integration with their existing workflow, ability to add collaborators with different levels of privacy, and selecting which components and files to make public or private.

When did the institution establish their relationship with your repository?

I think we became OSF institutional users in 2017. I began giving workshops in 2018, and then in 2019 or 2020 we became formal OSF Institutional members.

What support does the repository provider provide to the institution (e.g., implementation only, ongoing administration, data curation, etc.)?

OSF handled the initial setup, including branding and SSO, and continues to maintain the platform. We have access to usage data through their institutional dashboard, and their support team is responsive when we run into technical issues or questions about integrations with tools like OneDrive or GitHub. In fact, we worked closely with them when they rolled out the institutional OneDrive option to help get it set up. We recently added a departmental attribute to the SSO so that we can record the unit affiliation of our institutional users in addition to receiving aggregate counts of monthly OSF logins and use. OSF also provides training materials and occasional webinars, which we've used to help introduce the platform to researchers. While they don't curate data themselves, the platform includes useful features for managing and sharing research materials responsibly.

[Responses continue on next page]

Survey Response from Ben Gorham

Research Data and GIS Specialist at Case Western Reserve University

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Open Science Framework (OSF) - <https://osf.io/institutions/cwru>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

Cost, openness, ease of use, integration with SSO, DOIs, privacy, file size

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

A great extent. Anything we do needs to support those policies.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

Yes. Cost and need to collaborate with numerous other campus departments to build one out made it untenable at the moment.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

No.

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

Faculty, students, staff. Datasets, papers, posters, collaborative projects, ELNs, preprints.

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

Self-deposit with occasional library oversight/curation.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

Branding

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

Engineering departments most common, then biomed

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

All of the above.

Is there a repository feature or function that you find particularly useful, interesting, and/or enjoyable to use?

Click and drag to upload, ease of DOI minting

When did the institution establish their relationship with your repository?

2019.

What support does the repository provider provide to the institution (e.g., implementation only, ongoing administration, data curation, etc.)?

Implementation, technical support and guidance, roadmap participation.

[Responses continue on next page]

Survey Response from Matthew Mariner

Data Curator Librarian at University of Rochester | <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3479-0960>

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Figshare - <https://rochester.figshare.com/>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

I think the main features were DOI assignation, compliance with NIH, and Figshare's general acceptance in the community/ Granted, this was before my time, and the provenance of those decisions are muddy, but our previous repository, which was home grown over a decade ago, was simply not satisfying the current needs of researchers or funders.

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

It was originally considered because of the Nelson Memo and forthcoming (then) NIH data access mandates. I'd say between that and the deprecation of our former repository were the key factors.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

No.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

Our former repository was outdated with a very complicated database designed in-house by former employees, so it became of a sort of black box. We needed a modern solution for IR-type materials and, specifically data. Cultural resources were (or are being) moved to other platforms like Omeka and Preservica.

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

Our users run the gamut of biomedical researchers, electrical engineers, and student researchers just setting foot into publishing (undergraduate research is a focus, for example). Right now most of the data is typically tabular and submitted due to publisher mandates, but we suspect influxes of NIH, DOE, and NSF data once those earlier cycles complete. And we are currently migrating out ETDs from our previous repository to Figshare, so we hope to restrict it to scholarly output, data, and code (we have several student and faculty XR researchers that

are availing themselves of Figshare for things like Unity packages and related OER materials).

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

We encourage self-deposit but have mediation for all materials, as we ensure all materials go through a curation process that checks, among other things, presence of PII or PHI; file organization; accessibility; and metadata enrichment.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

So far we have not added more than the standard branding customization, but are getting more into custom fields which was precipitated by the ETD migration, which requires at least 8-10 specific fields not provided by Figshare out of the box. We are also looking into allowing access-restricted data, or data access mediated by the owner.

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

Most data submitted now is for small-scale research projects or those mandated by publishers, but as I said, we expect that to shift as funding cycles complete. Lately we have seen lots of data from researchers in Earth and Environmental Sciences and Biomedical Engineering. Sizes tend to be rather small and types tabular. Unfortunately we simply do not have the space to accommodate large amounts of medical imaging like DICOM, but are definitely seeing more interest from researchers in helping them store those data.

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

I feel we definitely have better discovery, stats tracking, and compliance, but the biggest gain is simply in having support! As I said, our previous repo is an enigma with almost no documentation, so being able to work with Figshare and focus on curation has been a relief.

Is there a repository feature or function that you find particularly useful, interesting, and/or enjoyable to use?

It sounds simplistic, but simply having the ability to reserve DOIs and not worry about working directly with Datacite or Crossref to manage them is a step up. I do also like Figshare's ability to accept intact folder structures, which is helpful when researchers have, maybe not large sizes of data, but want to retain the logic of their data's directory.

When did the institution establish their relationship with your repository?

I believe it was in or around 2022/2023

What support does the repository provider provide to the institution (e.g., implementation only, ongoing administration, data curation, etc.)?

Ongoing administration, if understand the term correctly (stability, implementation of new features, tech support etc.).

[Responses continue on next page]

Survey Response from a Research Librarian

Research Data Librarian at Johns Hopkins University

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Vivli - <https://vivli.org/ourmember/johns-hopkins/>

What repository feature requirements were considered?

Our institution conducts a lot of medical research. We needed a solution for sharing this type of research that also protected our participants.

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

I did not work at our institution when we became Vivli members. My understanding is that we became members many years before the 2023 NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy. Given that, I would conjecture that the desire to become Vivli members was likely greater than simply needing to comply with funder policies, and was also done from a place of wanting to contribute to open science.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

While we do operate an open-access repository, which runs on Dataverse Project software, the administrative burden of running a controlled-access is too steep for us at the moment. Also, while Vivli is considered a generalist repository, I would argue that it straddles the line between disciplinary and generalist. My advice to researchers is to find a disciplinary repository first, and then move to a generalist repository and Vivli is a good place for clinical data.

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

Researchers are the primary users of the repository. They publish data, code, and documentation.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

Vivli has kindly worked with us with respect to non-standard limitations for some of our datasets. <https://vivli.org/ourmember/johns-hopkins/>

Survey Response from a Research Librarian

Research & Education Librarian at a R1 Institution

What GREI member repository does your institution work with or use as a provider?

Vivli

What repository feature requirements were considered?

Our research institution needs access to a controlled access repository option for human clinical trials/clinical data for our researchers. The data repository needs to provide dataset DOIs, plan for long-term sustainability, & provide security/integrity/controls for sensitive data.

To what extent did institutional, funder, or government data sharing policy requirements influence the decision?

I was not here at the time our institution joined Vivli so I cannot say though it was early enough to be pre-GREI initiative and pre NIH data management and sharing policy.

Did your institution consider building its own custom repository solution? If yes, why did the institution opt to work with a GREI repository instead?

We have our own data repository but it is an open access repository and therefore not suitable for sensitive human subjects data.

Did the GREI repository replace an existing institutional repository? If so, please elaborate on the decision to replace.

Vivli does not replace our institutional repository, it supplements it by providing a controlled access option for human subjects clinical data.

Who are the users of your repository (e.g., faculty, students, specific disciplines) and what items do they publish in it (e.g., data, software/code, theses/dissertations, preprints, etc.)?

To date, mostly clinical research faculty/researchers publishing clinical trial data.

How does your institution administer the repository (e.g., self-deposit, mediated submission, quality control checks, etc.) and to what extent are submitted data/other objects curated?

We do not.

How has your GREI repository provider customized the repository for your institution (e.g., branding, metadata fields, optional features, integrations, etc.)?

We are institutional members of Vivli

What trends in repository usage have you observed (e.g., departments that deposit the most data, most common type(s) or data, sizes of datasets, funders of research, etc.)?

With the implementation of the 2023 NIH data management and sharing policy, we have observed an increase in the number of researchers who in their DMSP submitted with their NIH grant state that they will deposit their data in Vivli.

How has your institution benefitted from working with your repository provider to support data sharing? (e.g., improved discovery, impact tracking, compliance, interoperability, technical/financial sustainability, etc.)

We have benefited through improved discovery of our data sets, the ability to show that our researchers are compliant with sharing their data, and the ability to track data sharing in Vivli as reported by periodic Vivli reports.

When did the institution establish their relationship with your repository?

2018 (we joined Vivli as a founding member organization)

What support does the repository provider provide to the institution (e.g., implementation only, ongoing administration, data curation, etc.)?

Vivli provides support to researchers who are depositing data (when researcher contacts Vivli), management of data use requests.

